

Exploring the gustatory and the olfactory systems through interactive activities: the undergraduate student's version.

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Faculty who wish to run this activity with their undergraduate students need to request the instructor's version which contains the following: a list of items to purchase, the preparation guide, the time and class management guide, the possible variants of the activities, the tips to consider, the possible ways to collect student's data using learning management system or online surveys and the answers to the worksheet. To request the instructor's version, please send an email using your professional address with your name, position, institution, class level to the following email: ghb2002@qatar-med.cornell.edu.

Background

Gustation and Olfaction are sensory pathways that are continuously used by humans. Both play an important role in environmental perception and cognition. They are also involved in complex processes of interaction with other bodily systems and regions of the brain. Gustation and olfaction will be explored via guided-learning through a set of eight interactive stations. The eight stations have been developed for students to discover and experiment with the complexity of gustation and olfaction and their interactions with each other. This lab is designed to complement lecture material on gustatory and olfactory pathways to the brain and concludes with a multiple choice questions.

Important instructions for participants

This lab involves ingesting food items.

Students must inform instructors of food allergy prior to beginning the lab. Failure to report allergies may result in illness or injury.

Students should retrieve one materials kit and retain it throughout the entire lab. This kit will contain: 1 blindfold, 1 nose clip/plug, 1 large cup for water, paper towels, 14 small cups for soda, 2 plates, 1 cotton bud/cotton swab.

Students will choose a partner, put on their 'game face' and be prepared to explore taste and smell. This means that students are expected to refrain from telling their partners what is being smelled/tasted when perception could be influenced by such knowledge.

Students can begin at any station, except for number 8, which will be done at the end as a class.

Students will need their lab notebook - to record all of your observations.

At the end of lab, students will complete a worksheet and a survey about the lab.

STATION 1: TASTER TYPE TEST

Test Description: At this station, you will be using a blue dye to determine which taste type you are.

Caution: You will be using food colorant at this station. Please check that you're not sensitive to any of the ingredients.

Test Instructions:

1. Place a cotton bud into the bottle of blue food dye until it is coated.
2. Stick your tongue out & dry it with a paper towel.
3. Using the mirror provided, coat the front third of your tongue with the dye.
4. Next, carefully place a paper ring on to your tongue. You may stack two paper rings together to help with stability. The blue dye will stain the tongue but slide off the prominent pink bumps known as papillae. Each bump contains three to five taste buds.
5. Using the mirror provided, count the number of pink bumps inside the paper ring. Try to keep your tongue still.
 - Alternatively, you may ask a friend to count for you. The magnifying glass provided may assist your partner in obtaining an accurate count.
 - A final option to obtain the papillae count would be for your partner to take a photo of your tongue and zoom in on the image.
6. Compare your papillae numbers to the chart below to identify your taster type.

Taster Type	Non-Taster	Average Taster	Supertaster
Number of Papillae	<15	15-35	>35

7. Record your papillae count in the box below.

8. Tidy before moving to next station!

STATION 2: JELLY BEAN TEST

Test Description: At this station, you will be exploring flavors and the role of olfactory pathway in flavor detection.

Test Instructions:

1. Install blindfold and nose clips on Partner 1 (P1).
2. Partner 2 (P2) gives P1 a whole jelly bean - without indicating the flavor.
3. P1 chews whole bean and guesses the flavor.
4. P2 records the results in the box below.
5. Repeat for other two flavors.
6. Switch roles with your partner and repeat the steps.
7. Clean up station, before moving on to next!
8. Take notes of your observations in the box below.

STATION 3: SALIVA TEST

Test Description: At this station, you will be testing the impact of saliva on flavor identification. You will be tasting food with a dry tongue.

CAUTION: Items containing gluten/nuts will be used in this test!

Test Instructions:

1. Install blindfold and nose clip on P1.
2. P2 will select two food items and place them on a plate.
3. P1 will dry tongue with paper towel -- tongue must be **VERY** dry! (Drying your tongue looks pretty silly, but we are all doing it).
4. P2 hands P1 a sample; P1 places the sample on the DRY tongue & guesses the identity of the food--without chewing!
5. P2 records P1's guess in box below.
6. P1 washes mouth out with water.
7. Repeat steps 3-6 for the second food item.
8. Switch roles and repeat all steps.
9. Tidy station prior to moving on!

STATION 4: SOFT DRINK TEST

Test Description: You will be tasting & identifying soft drinks with and without the help of all of your senses (eg: sight & smell).

Test Instructions:

1. Install blindfold and nose clip on P1.
2. P2 pours a **small** amount of each soft drink in a different cup.
3. P1 takes a sip of each & guesses flavor for each.
4. P2 records P1's guesses in the box below.
5. Remove nose clip from P1. Keep blindfold in place.
6. Repeat steps 2-4 again.
7. Remove both blindfold and nose clip and repeat process of tasting small amounts.
8. Don't forget to record results.
9. Switch roles and repeat steps 1-8 for P2.
10. Tidy station before moving on to the next!

STATION 5: FLAVOR TRIPPING TEST 1

Test Description: You will be tasting one food item, while smelling another.

- You will need to help each other a bit more with this one!
- To avoid biasing results, some of the sets are covered.

There are two sets of food (A & B). Each food set has 4 containers.

CAUTION: There are a variety of food items used in this experiment (which we are reluctant to divulge, so as not to influence your experience). Please let us know of any food allergies you may have, before taking part in the experiment!

Test Instructions:

Food [Set A](#) (for P1): 2 containers labeled « smell »
2 containers labeled « taste »

Food [Set B](#) (for P2): 2 containers labeled « smell »
2 containers labeled « taste »

1. Install blindfold on P1.
2. Partner 2 uncovers [Set A](#).
3. P2 removes one « smell » item and places item under P1's nose.
4. P2 gives P1 the « taste » item for tasting.
5. P1 smells & tastes food items together—**smelling and tasting should be done simultaneously.**
6. P1 guesses tasted item.
7. P2 records the guess in box below.
8. P1 washes mouth/tongue with water.
9. Repeat process with second set of containers in [Set A](#).
10. P2 records the guess n box below.
11. Switch roles and repeat same process for P2 using [Set B](#)—the set that has not been uncovered by this point.
12. Tidy station prior to moving on!

STATION 6: FLAVOR TRIPPING TEST 2

Test Description: At this station, you will be tasting 8 drinks. Only have a sip, ALWAYS wash mouth with water between each drink.

Test Instructions:

1. Install blindfold & nose clip on P1.
2. P2 pours 4 small bits of all of the provided drinks in separate cups.
3. P1 tastes/sips each one of them— Sipping water between each cup to cleanse mouth.
4. Record results in box below.
5. Remove nose clips (keeping blindfold in place), P1 repeats tasting the 4 drinks — with water in-between every taste.
6. Record results in box below.
7. Repeat procedure one more time for P1 w/o blindfold or nose clips.
8. Record observations in box below.
9. Switch roles and repeat process for P2.
10. Tidy station before walking to the next!

STATION 7: FLAVOR TRIPPING 3

Test Description

You will sample three different colored gelatins and identify their flavor. No blindfold or nose clips are needed for this station.

Test Instructions

1. P1 & 2 taste the same samples at the same time.
2. Use spoon to scoop a small sample of gelatin.
3. Guess the flavor.
4. Record the guess in the box below.
5. Repeat for two other colors of gelatin and record results.
6. Smell the gelatin and record your observations in the box below.

STATION 8: FLAVOR TRIPPING TEST 4

Test Description: We will complete station 8 as a class. You will eat a substance called Miracle Berry and then taste a variety of food items. No blindfold or nose plugs are needed for this test.

CAUTION: If you are allergic to berries of any kind, DO NOT PARTICIPATE IN THIS STATION!

Test Instructions:

1. Take one berry and chew it. Rub the berry on your tongue while chewing it to coat the tongue.
2. Wait 5 to 15 min for the Miracle Berry to take effect--coating entire tongue with fruit.
3. Remove 1 food item from each container and place it on your plate.
4. Taste each food item on your plate.
5. Record your observations in the box below.
6. Tidy the station.

WORKSHEET

Station 1: A supertaster (check all that apply)

- a. Is more sensitive to taste
- b. Is less sensitive to taste
- c. Might be a picky eater

Station 2: Which of the following is/are true(s):

- a. The reason why we cannot guess the flavor of jellybeans while having the nose clipped is because retro olfaction is blocked.
- b. Sweetness is mediated by retronasal olfaction.
- c. Sourness is mediated by retronasal olfaction.
- d. Orange flavor is mediated by retronasal olfaction.

Station 3: Which of the following is/are true(s):

- a. Saliva is not required in taste sensation.
- b. Saliva contains enzymes that breakdown food components.
- c. Saliva is only important for retronasal olfaction and not taste.

Station 4: Which of the following is/are true(s):

- a. The perception of carbonation is mediated by taste.
- b. The perception of carbonation is mediated by retronasal olfaction.

Station 5: Based on your knowledge of retronasal olfaction and taste, what would you expect from someone who taste a food item and smell a different one at the same time?

- a. To not be able to taste at all.
- b. To not be able to guess the correct flavor.
- c. He/she might get a taste illusion if the smell and taste sensory pathways stimulated together correspond to a different food item.

Station 6: In station 6, all drinks were only water and colorant. Why did we design this station?

- a. Vision can bias perception of taste and/or flavor and trigger an illusion of taste.
- b. Colorants are chemical components that bind to taste receptors for sweet.

Station 7: Which of the following is/are true?

- a. The gelatin was not sweet because no sweet molecules were present to bind to taste receptors.
- b. Retronasal olfaction could not happen because the gelatin was tasteless.
- c. Retronasal olfaction only happens if you chew the gelatin enough to release chemicals.

Station 8: Miraculin is

- a. An endogen reversible agonist of sweet receptors.
- b. An exogen reversible antagonist of sweet receptors.
- c. An endogen irreversible agonist of sweet receptors.
- d. An exogen irreversible antagonist of sweet receptors.
- e. An exogen reversible agonist of sweet receptors.